

BIM – A BOOSTER FOR ENERGY TRANSITION AND BIPV ADOPTION

Philippe Alamy⁽¹⁾, Van Khai Nguyen⁽²⁾, Erika Saretta⁽³⁾, Pierluigi Bonomo⁽³⁾, Eduardo Roman⁽⁴⁾, Jose Maria Vega de Seoane⁽⁴⁾, Pablo Alonso⁽⁵⁾

(1) ENERBIM Sarl

philippe.alamy@enerbim.com

(2) CADCAMATION KMR S.A.

vknguyen@cadcamation.ch

(3) SUPSI-ISAAC

erika.saretta@supsi.ch;

(4) FUNDACIÓN TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION

eduardo.roman@tecnalia.com

(5) WIP – WIRTSCHAFT UND INFRASTRUKTUR GMBH & CO PLANUNGS KG

pablo.alonso@wip-munich.de

ABSTRACT

Building-Integrated PhotoVoltaic (BIPV) has the potential to significantly contribute to the achievement of the demanding energy efficiency targets set by the EU. However, its market uptake has been hindered in the past years by the difficulties of the industry in providing holistic solutions complying with key demands from decision makers and end-users. Practically, among the most important technological challenges toward energy-efficient buildings are twofold: (i) bioclimatic design, considering eco-friendly sources as well as renewable and durable materials, and (ii) Building Information Modelling (BIM) methodology for the whole architecture, engineering and construction (AEC), involving design, production and process innovation respectively. The fragmentation of the value chain, especially in BIPV where building and electro-technical sectors need to work in a coordinated way, is a real threat to the competitiveness of the sector. In fact, a considerable share of cost for BIPV systems is not only related to the product (module, BOS, etc.), manufacturing and operation but also to inefficiencies along some project stages. So far, BIPV is still not supported by a completely digitized process which could ensure clear structures, efficient processes, lower costs, less time and higher quality across the entire lifecycle. Overcoming these challenges can be achieved by the implementation of BIM into the BIPV value-chain, in order to introduce an integrated process supported by digital and interoperable environments connected, from pre-design to manufacturing, as a key to address growing technical complexity and manufacturing flexibility. Digitalization can overcome the construction processes fragmentation and communication problems between stakeholders, to reduce on-site time for installation and improve building affordability throughout its lifecycle. Within this context, two European H2020 projects, PVSITES (www.pvsites.eu) and BIPVBOOST (www.bipvboost.eu), address the need for a software solution within a digital environment for the joint modelling, performance simulation and information management of BIPV and building energy systems.

Keywords: BIPV, BIM, EPBD, PVSITES, BIPVBOOST

1 EUROPEAN AMBITION

On the one hand, PVSITES project has released a fully functional beta version of a SaaS (Software as a Service) platform, BIM-compatible, designed to ease the integration of BIPV systems in buildings at the design stage, covering the electrical, thermal and optical domains. On the other hand, BIPVBOOST activities will provide a clear definition of the reference BIPV process, including its information management, optimization strategies and KPIs for cost-reduction and will develop advanced features to extend the effectiveness of the existing BIM-based software solutions. As a result, both projects will contribute to the uptake of BIPV implementation and its integration within a holistic BIM process. The overall ambition of this study is to merge high-performance computing, scientific models and methodologies for energy modelling, user-friendly software tools and web-based services, together with collaborative processes supporting sustainable design towards NZEB/Positive Energy Buildings, active skins and the emerging Building Integrated Photovoltaic technology (BIPV).

1.1 Information Management

Historically, CAD software represented 2D geometry based on wireframe graphical elements. More complex information, such as the relationships between graphical elements, could not be added. More recently, object-oriented CAD systems replaced graphical symbols with building primitives or objects, capable of representing the characteristics of physical objects like mechanical components or building elements. These building elements can be parametrically calculated and displayed in multiple views, and non-graphic attributes can be assigned to them as “information”, thus enabling such elements or objects to become “smart” (parametric, contextual). This combination of parametric 3D geometry with assigned rules and dimensions represents, therefore, the “single source of truth” and allows the representation of complex geometric and functional relationships between building elements. Building Information Modeling/Management (BIM) was initially conceived as the latest generation of object-oriented CAD systems, in which all the intelligent building objects that constitute the architectural and structural design can co-exist within a single virtual structure that captures everything known about the whole entity.

Figure 1: the BIM story – The rise of Information Management

1.2 BIM innovation

BIM success is all about holistic approach towards understanding the whole AEC (Architecture, Engineering & Construction) building process and streamlining the data and workflow through the entire project lifespan in order to achieve efficient and quality projects that match with energy and carbon transition targets [1]. The major challenge of this forward-looking digital planning method is to provide comprehensive building performance analyses at the early stage of the building design process while implementing different computational technologies that exist across multiple domains into the conceptual BIM model.

PVSITES and BIPVBOOST objectives to reinforce the BIPV industry with a BIM approach are:

- Clear definition of the reference BIPV process, current bottlenecks, strategies and information categories to optimize the workflow and collaboration for cost and work-time reduction, thus enhancing productivity,
- Development of advanced optimization features in a multicriteria approach (energy efficiency, comfort, system cost, load matching) for BIM based software solution BIMSolar® (currently providing coupled PV and building energy performance simulation of BIPV systems) along the whole value-chain in order to analyse BIPV scenarios against criteria of the minimal cost-to-power ratio, reducing times in decision phases,
- Interfacing BIM with general design to technical design, manufacturing and procurement stages, enhancing interoperability with façade integrators, roof specialists and producers,
- Transition from a software tool to a collaborative platform to support an optimal teamwork between the stakeholders, reducing risks and enhancing cooperation of project teams along the entire BIPV project lifecycle, including operation and maintenance.

2 BIM STRATEGIES for BIPV

Seamless integration among the tools and between design models and building energy analysis models is proposed based on an advanced BIM-based platform. This integrated approach towards sustainable design is

expected to efficiently provide energy performance analyses based upon multiple computations at the early design phase with coupled optimization algorithms and readjusted throughout the whole lifespan of the building based on real-world captured data (Digital Twin concept). Integrated BIM with a consistent and structured data management is the key to generate such a digital twin model whose dynamic performance can be used by simulation tools for a variety of different boundary conditions.

Considering the intrinsic multidisciplinary domain of BIPV, that is both an electrical and building element characterized by several different requirements coming from different disciplines, a BIM-based BIPV process is proposed to cope with all BIPV related aspects and involve BIPV stakeholders in a collaborative and interoperable environment to avoid inefficiencies, bottlenecks and pitfalls, thus reducing costs. In accordance with this perspective, an information management strategy and an information modelling strategy are needed for overcoming current bottlenecks and control costs along the value chain.

2.1 Digital roadmap for BIPV

However, such an integrated process calls for a dedicated new approach for BIPV and building performance analysis requires a global and advanced calculation method based on multi-domain simulations. In the framework of the PVSITES project, ray tracing algorithms [2] has been integrated to model solar radiation interaction with complex urban environments and its effects, starting with the 3D computation of total irradiance at elementary level in the virtual scene then calculation of the hourly to yearly PV production from module to building level.

Figure 2: Irradiance distribution using ray tracing and coupled PV production – PVSITES carport (FLISOM)

Passive solar heating and lighting are important issues to be taken into consideration in order to develop façade or roof solutions to reduce energy consumption in new buildings together with the design of innovative BIPV products. Our roadmap addresses the very beginning of the conceptual design, supporting appropriate building intrinsic performance (bioclimatic architecture) and energy efficient systems and technologies, such as solar systems (solar architecture).

In order to respond to the different existing building typologies, offering a broad and flexible range of BIPV solutions (BIPV material + integration features) at a reduced cost is a must, with a focus on the common building stock. Our aim is to offer the widest range of solutions for the building skin with enhanced flexibility of design, products, aesthetical values and cost-competitive in relation to their traditional, non-PV counterparts.

AR (augmented reality) application is considered to foster BIPV real interventions on the construction market, by showcasing to potential investors a BIPV architectural scenario on a building in its proposed real-world location, helping them understand how the asset will connect with its surroundings as well as to estimate preliminary energy production.

2.2 BIM Objects for BIPV

Today CAD blocks, so far used to create repeated contents, such as drawing symbols or standard components, are replaced by BIM objects [3]. BIM objects still carry the representation of products in 2D and 3D like a CAD block would, but they also carry so much more in terms of information. The digital product in BIM environment is usually as close as possible to the physical AEC real product both for 3D representation and with the correct information and properties (materials, costs, maintenance, etc.). Accordingly, the model element can be developed in reference to a Level of Development (LOD). BIPV-BIM objects families that can be used by architects, contractors and other players are a key-aspect of BIPV digitalization, making possible to consider and share the BIPV design with all the stakeholders since the first phase of the project along the process work stages. Thanks to a BIM-based process, the BIPV BIM object can be integrated in the whole AEC process.

BIPV components can be conceived collaboratively and verified virtually, before it will be built for real, reducing the problems in construction and operation. The development of a BIM object, in order to reproduce the real features of the constructive component both in terms of geometry and information according to the LOD concerned, usually requires detailed and precise parametric information. Typically, the “digital families” represent common building components made available by industries in catalogues and that can be uploaded in the project model (e.g. furnishing objects, constructive parts, etc.). The main challenge for developing a BIM object in case of a customizable BIPV component is that all the main object’s features are not fixed or pre-defined but rather they can be established case by case during the design phase. The level of dynamics required as interactions of the object with its virtual environment is very high, compared to other BIM object (such as sanitary equipment or even classic windows).

From module shape to type and arrangement of cells, e.g. up to the panel layering and materials, everything can be customized, generating in each case a completely different layout of the component with different properties and performance. In this perspective the conventional strategy to develop a library of BIPV BIM objects through a catalogue can be not effective, and the development of a certain adaptability of the component is needed. A digital family is a group of elements with a common set of properties, called parameters, and a related graphical representation. In BIM software environment like Autodesk® Revit®, loadable families are used to create building components that would usually be purchased, delivered, and installed in and around a building, such as windows, doors, casework, fixtures, furniture, and planting.

As already introduced, the implementation of the digitized approach will be carried out through BIMSolar®

environment which so far represents one of the most advanced software for BIPV design and simulation at element level, e.g. BIPV BIM objects, also ensuring an advanced level of interoperability with common architectural BIM software.

BIMSolar® enables:

- Creating a virtual BIPV module from manufacturers datasheets, generating dynamic set-up related to building shape,
- Adequacy between simulation and computation process – within the software - and Autodesk® Revit® requirements to generate families of objects using BIM interoperability with xml-based language,
- Stepping from element level to building level, thanks to BIM data exchange: BIPV layouts to sustain overall building skin performance.

A large portfolio of BIPV BIM objects (products’ digital twins) based on crystalline silicon and flexible thin film CIGS technologies is proposed to designers, manufacturers and installers, bridging the gap between design, manufacturing and energy management solutions.

Figure 3: PVSITES software - BIPV layouts

Figure 4: PVSITES software - BIPV parametric object

Figure 5: BIPV BIM object as Autodesk® Revit® families

Figure 6: BIPV BIM layouts - Autodesk® Revit®

3 SCIENTIFIC INNOVATION AND RELEVANCE

BIM and BIPV have both a large innovation potential based on the virtualization of active buildings skins from material element to façade or roof integrated solutions, as well as connection to energy management technologies, and associated software tools to support the design process.

Even though there are few commercial BIM software offering the change to evaluate standard PV module performance, the integration of PV in building envelopes such as BIPV is not completely embedded today in BIM processes and BIM solutions, whereas BIM is the main booster for the building industry, fostering innovation at every stage of the value chain while supporting costs reduction and risk mitigation.

BIPV performance can be anticipated, meaning simulated, computed and visualized using BIMSolar[®], the BIM-based software developed within both the PVSITES and BIPVBOOST projects. Indeed, many decision-making criteria are available to help building designers optimize the electrical production (PV), the induced thermal comfort of the designed BIPV implementation, while minimizing the building energy needs, to achieve NZEB and Positive Energy Building targets:

- Irradiance simulation and mapping, including albedo settings, within full 3D user interface,
- Electrical production figures and histograms (from array yield to DC/AC production and final yield) including self-consumption or feed-in scenarios,
- The impact on energy needs of the building (other than purely electrical demand). Two indicators are affected by BIPV systems: heating and cooling demands,
- The impact on thermal occupant comfort (Givoni Comfort Zones).

Monte Carlo raytracing methodology is used to compute accurately the complex phenomenon of irradiance on the building skin, considering direct and diffuse radiation, as well as multiple reflections on the surrounding environment. This spatial distribution of irradiance feed BIPV electrical and thermal models integrated into the simulation software, sourcing in the same time materials or products features provided by BIPV BIM objects.

Figure 6: raytracing concept

Figure 7: Irradiance, BIPV modules and 3D user interface PIZ demo site #4 (BIPVBOOST)

Libraries of standardized BIPV products and related PVSITES and BIPVBOOST solutions are turned into BIM components, introduced into the BIM market as new digital asset, bridging the gap between architects, engineers and PV manufacturers as BIM is first and for the most a collaborative methodology generating collaborative workspaces.

These BIPV virtual components aggregate interoperable parameters directly into the main BIM tools, enabling experts (envelop designers, façade makers, energy planners) to implement a collaborative Product Information Management process.

Within BIPVBOOST project, an advanced extension of the existing BIM-based BIPV web platform and simulation software for the simulation of PV and building energy performance of BIPV systems will be implemented. This fact will allow to extend, optimize and focus the virtual model for the key-stages of the BIPV process to support the cost reduction through a data driven approach. The platform developed herein is intended to ensure interoperability along design, manufacturing and installation phases, with the goal to reduce the cost of BIPV by enhancing the process. The tool functionalities extension will act as a decision support tool for all the main stages of the BIPV process, including optimization engine based on PARETO frontier methodology.

4 RESULTS AND CONCLUSION

Integrating photovoltaics in building skin thanks to BIPV involves a strong integration of energy, electrical, architectural and construction aspects and requirements during the whole process, requiring a multidisciplinary and integrated approach by architects, engineers and manufacturers since the initial design stages. The construction industry is experiencing real and measurable impacts from the adoption of BIM, especially for the opportunity to manage efficiently project's complexities and multidisciplinary. This impact is not just due to the software but to how it alters industry, design and construction processes, encouraging collaboration, prefabrication and other ways to make those processes more productive. The following impacts are expected from the work performed by PVSITES and BIPVBOOST:

- The proposed software tool for the coupled simulation of BIPV elements and building energy performance will be (as of today) the only tool in the market offering this integrated approach both for standard and innovative PV and BIPV products. BIM and Energy Modelling

will support and guarantee architectural and engineering workflows, as data will be added and exchanged through virtual workspaces, and even directly connected to the manufacturers' databases.

- The use of a BIM-based workflow will enable an enhanced collaboration platform for stakeholders along the BIPV value chain, saving costs in terms of effective introduction of BIPV from the early design phase and supporting information exchange during manufacturing, installation and facility operation.
- Cost-reductions are foreseen along the design and execution process of BIPV project. This action will ease the assessment of BIPV technologies under the Energy Plus Building Directive (EPBD) framework, designing and accurately calculating the impact of a specific BIPV solution on the energy performance of a given building, in terms of energy consumption reduction based on passive properties, and on-site electricity generation capacity to cover building's energy needs.
- At least 10-15% of cost savings in the project stage should be generated from BIM within the actual BIPV processes.

Once actioned, the combination of the results of these researches developed in a BIM-based perspective are supposed to support all BIPV stakeholders and partners to stay on course on implementing a digitized approach for the BIPV process.

5 REFERENCES

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